

Enhanced delignification and saccharification of rice straw by ionic liquid or surfactant assisted biological pretreatment

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1. Introduction

Lignocellulosic biomass (LCB) conversion to bioethanol is a practical option for the improvement of energy security and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Rice straw is an abundant waste biomass worldwide with the potential to produce 730 billion liters of bioethanol per year (Binod *et al.*, 2010).

Pretreatment of LCB is required to enhance the accessibility of rice straw for the conversion of cellulose into fermentable sugars. Enzymatic pretreatments have been extensively studied because they are very inexpensive and have low energy and mild environmental condition requirements compared with other pretreatment methods (Mutschlechner *et al.*, 2015). Laccase is a multicopper oxidase enzyme that oxidizes substituted phenols, a small percentage of lignin, using molecular oxygen as the final electron acceptor. However, this pretreatment process needs to be improved because of the low efficiency of bio-based delignification methods.

Recently, studies indicated that the combination of pretreatment processes with biological pretreatment increases the lignin removal and enzymatic digestibility. The application of ionic liquids (IL) and surfactants has been recommended to improve the pretreatment methods (Chang *et al.*, 2016; Qing *et al.*, 2010); however, the combination of ILs and surfactants with a biodelignification process has not been reported in a single system.

The objective of this study was therefore to enhance the biodelignification pretreatment of rice straw using laccase in the presence of [AMIM]Cl or TritonX-100. The concentrations of [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 for high lignin removal were also investigated. The effect of the pretreatment was evaluated by performing enzymatic saccharification using different strategies. The changes in morphology and structure of the pretreated and untreated rice straw were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2. Materials and Methods

Rice straw (0.5 g) was pretreated with laccase (2U/g substrate) or along with [AMIM]Cl (100–1000 mg/L) or TritonX-100 (100–1000 mg/L). Pretreatment was carried out at shaking incubated flasks (50°C, 150 rpm, 24 h). Materials were washed with

deionized H₂O until pH 7.0 and dried (60°C, 24 h). Solid recovery and composition of the untreated and pretreated rice straw were analyzed (Jung *et al.*, 2015).

The enzymatic saccharification was performed using 2.5% of rice straw in 0.1 M sodium citrate buffer (pH 4.8) with 0.02% of sodium azide. The substrates were hydrolyzed using cellulase (Novozyme NS220086; 50 FPU/g substrate) and β -glucosidase (Novozyme NS221118; 40 CBU/g substrate) on a shaking incubator (150 rpm, 72 h, 50°C). The samples were then centrifuged (10000 rpm, 10 min). The total reducing sugar was determined by dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) method (Miller, 1959) and detected by UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Youke UV 756CRT, China; 575 nm). Four parallel conditions were conducted for pretreated rice straw before enzymatic saccharification: (1) filtration and wash with distilled water until pH 7.0; (2) boiling at 100°C for 20 min; (3) no filtration and wash and (4) simultaneous pretreatment-saccharification. All experiments were performed in triplicate and reported by average.

Characterizations of untreated and pretreated rice straw were done using a field-emission SEM (JEOL JSM-7001F, Japan).

3. Results

The lignin content gradually decreases with increasing [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 concentrations. The highest lignin removal, 31.79% and 18.49%, was observed when 500 mg/L TritonX-100 and 750 mg/L [AMIM]Cl, respectively, were added. The surfactant has a hydrophilic and a hydrophobic side and can bind to both lignin (hydrophobic side) and water (hydrophilic side), pulling the lignin into the water and enhancing its solubility (Qing *et al.*, 2010), hence, its addition to delignification improves the lignin removal efficiency. In addition, IL is also known to be capable of lignin removal, which might have practical advantages for the enzymatic saccharification of cellulose. Thus, the best concentrations of [AMIM]Cl and TritonX-100 were used for the next runs.

The pretreatment of rice straw with laccase only, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, or laccase + TritonX-100 led to an effective lignin removal of 11.96%, 18.49%, and 31.75%, respectively. Adding 500 mg/L TritonX-100 generated the highest lignin removal, enhancing it by 22.52%, compared with the sole laccase pretreatment. Results strongly supports the enancement of IL or surfactant on lignin removal. Also, the hemicellulose percentage decreased at pretreated rice straws. Hemicellulose removal increases the surface area and reduces unproductive enzyme binding and therefore increases the probability of cellulose to be hydrolyzed (Jeoh *et al.*, 2007).

The percentage of cellulose conversion from untreated and pretreated rice straws using four enzymatic saccharification strategies were shown in Fig.1. Laccase pretreatment significantly increases the cellulose conversion efficiency compared with untreated rice straw. The highest cellulose conversion, 40.96%, 38.24%, and 37.91%, was obtained after 72 h of enzymatic hydrolysis when the substrate was washed with distilled water after laccase + TritonX-100, laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and laccase-only pretreatment, respectively (Fig. 1a). After 72 h of enzymatic saccharification, the cellulose conversion

via unfiltered substrate before enzymatic hydrolysis (Fig. 1c) and simultaneous pretreatment-saccharification (Fig. 1d) increased from untreated rice straw to laccase + TritonX-100. The cellulose conversion increased to 25.58% (laccase + TritonX-100), 24.95% (laccase + [AMIM]Cl, and 24.51% (laccase only) when the laccase was deactivated at 100°C for 20 min (Fig. 1b). This result indicates that the laccase might be inactive during pretreatment or it is inhibited by enzymatic saccharification. Although the cellulose conversion increased by deactivating the laccase, it is still lower than the yield obtained from substrate washed with distilled water because some of the compounds generated via lignin degradation caused a decrease in the cellulose conversion yield. Therefore, the higher cellulose conversion yield using washed substrate indicates that there are enzyme inhibitions associated with pretreatment that can be removed by washing.

The SEM images of rice straw revealed the untreated rice straw exhibiting a smooth and rigid surface, whereas the surface of the pretreated rice straws with laccase pretreatments are broken into separated fibers and cracks occur on different levels because of the removal of lignin and hemicellulose (Zhao *et al.*, 2008). Most of the lignin and residual hemicellulose were removed during laccase and IL or surfactant pretreatment. The removal of both hemicellulose and lignin resulted in the release of a larger specific surface area and access to cellulose which favors the following enzymatic saccharification.

Figure 1. Profiles of enzymatic hydrolysis from rice straw pretreated by laccase with [AMIM]Cl or TritonX-100 and hydrolyzed (cellulase and β -glucosidase) by four treatments before the enzymatic saccharification: (a) filtration and wash with distilled water until pH 7.0; (b) boiling at 100°C for 20 min; (c) no filtration and wash; and (d) simultaneous pretreatment-saccharification.

4. Conclusion

In this study, IL and surfactant were used to enhance the performance of laccase with respect to pretreated rice straw. The highest cellulose conversion was 40.96% and 38.24% using a combined pretreatment with laccase + TritonX-100 (500 mg/L) and laccase + [AMIM]Cl (750 mg/L), respectively, after 72 h of enzymatic saccharification when the substrate was washed with distilled water. After laccase + [AMIM]Cl and laccase + TritonX-100 pretreatment, notable morphological changes were observed due to the increased specific surface area of rice straw. These results suggest that IL and surfactant can enhance the pretreatment performance of laccase and enzymatic saccharification.

References

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